

Influence of Capacity Building in the Management Reform on Service Delivery at Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company (NAWASSCO)

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ABSTRACT: Service delivery is the key issue in every business. The end result of each organization depends exclusively on the management of the resources. The management of water utilities has a rectifying effect to the water deficiency in most elements of the country. A significant reason behind poor access to water services in a geographic region is the inefficiencies of water utilities, particularly people who live in urban areas where they are totally dependent on a Water Service Provider. Water service is essential especially in urban area like Nakuru Town which is an emerging residential and industrial hub. The study sought to establish the influence of capacity building in the management reform on service delivery at Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company. An Ex-post facto research design was adopted for a sample of 223 clients and 113 staff of NAWASSCO. Data was collected using semi-structured questionnaires. Data analysis was using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS). The paper results yielded a correlation coefficient of $r = (269) = 0.323$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$ and regression coefficient of $\beta = 0.266$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$. This implies that capacity building have significant influence on service delivery. The paper recommends that staff members should be adequately trained to build their capacity in the delivery of quality services.

KeyWords: Capacity Building, Management Reform and Service Delivery

I. INTRODUCTION

There is currently rising agreement within the development community that capability development is the engine of human development. Within the face of the present economic, climate and food crisis, developing state and social group capacities to style and implement ways that minimize the impact exhibited by these crises can stay important for sustaining progress towards achieving development objectives as well as the property Development Goals. Decades of experimenting with development models have confirmed the worth of native possession and capability. Whereas monetary resources are very important, they alone cannot sustain human development. Technical cooperation is also applicable in some instances to deal with short-run desires; however, it tends to be donor-driven and pricey, and to bank unduly on foreign experience whereas distorting national priorities. Robust capability, regionally generated and sustained, is important to the success of any development enterprise. Without it, the integrity of development achievements will be compromised and progress will stay unsettled and illusive, separated from the capacities that exist already and liable to the progressively severe and sophisticated challenges facing the globe these days (Macdonald & Kam, 2017).

Many companies have different interpretations of building community capability than others. Some capacity building methods include fundraising, training centers, visits to the exhibition, support for office and documentation, on-job training, learning centers, and consultations. Developing nations implement -build one of the precursors to gaining an awareness of group capacity building and growth was the United Nations Development Program (UNDP). The UNDP has been providing guidance to its employees and governments on what was considered institution-building since the early 1970s. The United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR), formerly the UN Global Disaster Strategy in strategies to avoid being permanently dependent on foreign aid. Institutions and communities are actively promoting and increasing their capacity over time to achieve social and economic goals, including by enhancing knowledge, skills, structures and organizations, in a wider social and cultural context (Nussbaum, 2011).

The concept developed into the building of public capability in 1991. The UNDP describes capacity building in the society as a continuous long-term development process involving all stakeholders. This includes ministries, local authorities, NGOs, professionals, members of the community, academics, and more. The building of public capacity uses the social, science, technical, institutions and future capital. The aim of building community capacity is to solve policy-related issues and implementation strategies while taking into account the possible weaknesses and needs of the people involved. The UNDP outlines the individual, organizational, societal and non-training capacity building of the community (Paul, 2018).

The growing worries about climate change like local weather change, has been a focal point resulting to independent performance, performance that improves social, economic, and environmental factors in the lengthy run while defending the earth. During forums on way forward to acquire stable environment, it has come to be common to consist of talks about neighborhood social enablement as properly as related principles of involvement, belonging, agents, and bottom-up planning. For the communities to be independent, capacity building has become a quintessential phase of reaching sustainable development. Many organizations that do not belong to the government have ceased in inducing chronic aid dependency inside communities with the aid of developing initiatives and instead partner with them (Linn, 2016).

The reports and thoughts of Freire's from beforehand many years emphasized that no one ought to strengthen each person else and improvement had to be participatory. These arguments brought about the effectiveness of provider transport packages leading to development of capacity building. In September 2000, a commitment used to be sealed at the Millennium Declaration in New York by using a hundred ninety international locations with the goal of reaching the Millennium Development Goals by way of 2015. This commitment, which helped the nations, mainly the creating international locations to efficaciously and quickly respond to the modern-day world financial recession, local weather alternate and other crises, has sparked renewed pastime and engagement in ability boosting (Linn, 2016).

The United means of city and space encompasses a long history supporting the event and overall capability of non-profit organizations inside Calgary. For over a decade the organization has offered capability building grants in every form of areas, such as: analysis, Human Resources, leadership, and infrastructure support. Certainly, capacity building is the bone of contention for the past twenty years. This increased passion in capability boosting has resurfaced equally with the movement within the willingly and the public service groups pool of accessible finances, multiplied belief to try and use a lot with little, and generally public beliefs of irresponsibility. The differences inside arena are dedicated to form difficult tasks to structure property that generally prevents the flexibility of non-profits to try and perform duties that are productive. Unlikely donors have usually not acknowledged and supported the robust similar ways within the computing good results, structure ability and are advantaged on getting more property. Non-profit companies are advantaged on getting more donors for a particular with clearly seen results instead of releasing finances for their personal interests. Otherwise if structure capability is not strong, then operations, duties and tasks to be done are guaranteed to be unproductive (Macdonald & Kam, 2017).

Community capacity boosting is also described as the process of growing and strengthening the capability, feelings, strength, formulas and properties that groups and communities need to survive, adapt, and thrive in the fast-changing world. Community potential boosting is the issue that offers continuity, flexibility and functionality of a program/organization to adapt to the altering wishes of the populace served. Developing of roads and other works has been considered resource enablement of capacity building because it strengthens the ability of a project or creating public to improve business, projects, resource mobility and lifestyles (Smillie, 2001).

In the Nineteen Fifties and sixties, capacity building targeted on strengthening technology and group capabilities of persons in remote areas. In nineteen seventies, a collection of documents on worldwide projects strengthened the position on boosting potential for skills abilities in remote areas, additionally in the management sectors of growing areas. In the Nineteen Eighties the idea of organizational improvement improved tremendously. Organizational growth was once considered as a prolonged method of putting up or creating country's government, public and non-public region institutions, and NGOs. Although challenges on the ability to construct existed before, they were not integral subjects in worldwide projects envisioned through the 1990s. The introduction of potential developments as a main project thought in Nineteen Nineties occurred due to environment forces. (Morin, 2018)

In nineteen eighties, most small organizations were subjected to economic constraints- the neoliberal nature of programs led to low-income generations. In response, a sequence of changes in lifestyles had been enacted. The growing gap between the rich and the poor coupled with changes in life styles accelerated the emerging of non government

organizations in full swing. In nineteen nineties a new strategy was once positioned on the concept of independent project. Capacity building as path to personal independent growth (Colette, 2000).

Capability boosting thereof is the transition where one or the institution looks for the right skills through acquiring relevant training, implementing it, and ensuring the process continues. The knowledge acquired, materials used and other resources to increase the outcome are maintained. In this kind of knowledge, the organization is in a position of developing more professional employees in their current status. Capacity building also changes approach on how we view our society, how we behave and this leads to infrastructure enhancement. It makes us understand the challenges amongst people, government, non-government and other countries. When the organization realizes their goals and improves their skills it allows them to achieve their mandate. This objective will therefore strengthen the employees' skills, competencies and abilities, making them prone to challenges. It will also guide the internal developments and activities (Heslop, 2010).

One of the most fundamental thoughts that relates with capability building is the building of capacities in the government and creating countries so that they are in a position to manage environmental factors. Developing the capacity to control the factors affecting the economy reinforces capacity building within all countries. To hinder dictatorship in upcoming countries, a center of attention was positioned on growing capabilities and skills of countrywide and grassroots counties for the energy to be diffused throughout a state. Capability restructuring in the public servants encompasses presenting the equipment to assist them to fulfill their duties well and to the maximum. These encompasses reinforcing public service potential to plan their finances, accumulate income, innovate and put in force regulations, encourage barazas, be obvious and transparent and battle corruption (Tucker et al, 2011).

The paper was guided by the following set of study hypothesis;

- H₀: There is no significant influence of capacity building in the management reform on service delivery at Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company.
- H₁: There is a significant influence of capacity building in the management reform on service delivery at Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company.

II. METHODOLOGY

The study employed ex-post facto research design targeting the urban water service provider in Nakuru County of 230 employees and 45,000 customers. The choice of the organization's employees was prompted by the fact that these are the persons who execute the daily operations of the organization. The sample comprised of 223 clients and 113 staff of NAWASCO. Data was collected using semi-structured questionnaires. Data analysis was mainly quantitative in which the researcher used descriptions to evaluate the raw information for the purpose of obtaining the percentages of frequencies, means and standard deviations. Coefficient correlation and regression analysis were used to test the relationship between the study variables.

III. RESULTS

Table 1 Role of capacity building in the management reforms

Measurable Indicators	Very large	Large	moderate	Small	None
More service hours	55 (20.4%)	112 (41.6%)	49 (18.2%)	12 (4.5%)	41 (15.2%)
Good quality of water	93 (34.6%)	58 (21.6%)	104 (38.7%)	12 (1.5%)	2 (0.7%)
Affordable water tariffs	38 (14.1%)	56 (20.8%)	101 (37.5%)	56 (20.8%)	18 (6.7%)
Quantity of water supplied	11 (4.1%)	93 (34.6%)	92 (34.6%)	34 (12.6%)	39 (14.5%)

Source: (Researcher, 2019)

The outcome on Table 1 indicates most of the participants specified that to a large extent there was more service hours while the minority indicated to a small extent there was more service hours, these basically means consumers depended solely on the amount of water on that particular pipeline. The more the water produced the more the flow and vice versa while majority held the opinion that to a moderate extent there was good quality of water as a result of reformed management, the minority indicated to a no extent, meaning due to the capacity building amongst the employees, the motivation and more knowledge acquired had led to improved performance. The results also indicated that majority of the respondents were of moderate extent preferred that water tariffs were affordable now unlike before while the minority indicated there were affordable at a very large extent. Majority of the respondents held the opinion that to a large extent quantity of water supplied had improved as a result of reformed management while the minority disputed that it was to a no extent that quantity of water supplied had improved.

Table 2: The role of management reforms in the capacity building

Figure 1 results defines that a larger number of the engagers indicated that management reforms have a bigger share in the capability boosting of the organization with the following respondents holding a neutral opinion while the second last from the bottom respondents were in disagreement that management reforms have played a big role in the capacity building of NAWASSCO.

Table 3: Rate of effectiveness on service delivery as a result of reformed management

Measurable Indicators	Very effective	Effective	Slightly Effective	Neutral	Not Effective
Increased quantity of water	16(5.9%)	28(10.4%)	115(42.8%)	82(30.5%)	28(10.4%)
Improved water quality	13(4.8%)	23(8.6%)	122(45.4%)	86(32.0%)	25(9.3%)
Affordable water tariffs	9(3.3%)	17(6.3%)	24(8.9%)	91(33.8%)	128(47.8%)
Improved quality workforce training	55(20.4%)	65(24.2%)	61(22.7%)	60(22.3%)	28(10.4%)

Well organized management	10(3.7%)	123(45.7%)	24(8.9%)	93(34.6%)	19(7.1%)
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The outcomes on Table 3 indicates that most of the participants specified that increase in quantity of water was slightly effective as a result of reformed management, minority recommended that increase of water quantity was not very effective meaning the management needs to put more effort on other means of improving the same, while a third said that increased in quantity of water was not effective at all. Improvement in water quality was slightly effective as a result of reformed management majority indicated, minority recommended that it was very effective which is a very low number compared to the number of participants, a third were of the option that water quality improvement was not effective at all. The results indicate that affordability of water tariffs was not implemented even after the reforms had been effected that is for majority participants, meaning the water tariffs charged on the customers are still perceived to be very high, minority commented that they were very effective which is a very minimal number compared to the participants. While most respondents held the opinion that there was effective improvement of quality workforce training as a result of reformed management minority indicated that it was very minimal. Further, most respondents agreed that there was effective well organized management as a result of reformed management at NAWASSCO while minority indicated that the well organized management was very effective.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix

		Capacity Building in The Management Reforms		Service Delivery	
Capacity building in the management reforms	Pearson Correlation	1		.323**	
	p-value			.000	
	N	269		269	
Service Delivery	Pearson Relationship	.323**		.361**	
	p-value	.000		.000	
	N	269		269	

The tabulated outcome displays there exist significant correlation amid capacity building in the management reforms and service delivery in Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company ($r(269) = 0.323, p = 0.000 < 0.05$).

The regression analysis outcome indicates that there exists statistically relevant relation between capacity building in the management reforms and service delivery in Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company ($\beta = 0.266, p = 0.000 < 0.05$). Statistically, the 0.266 beta factor of capacity building in the management reforms implies that when capacity building in the management reforms is enhanced by an additional unit, service delivery in Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company increases by 0.266. This implies that capacity building in the management reforms have a positive impact on delivering of services in Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company.

This is true according to Macdonald and Kam (2017) where he states that currently rising agreement within the development community and the capability boosting is the fuel of employees’ productivity. With the current status of economic condition, weather and food crisis, developing state and social group capacities need to style and implement ways that minimize the impact exhibited by these crises and can stay important for sustaining progress towards achieving development objectives as well as the property development goals. Employees have therefore improved their skills and productivity after an offer of job training due to changes in the management leading to better returns in the organization.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Since the p-values for both correlation and regression analysis were less than 0.005, the null hypothesis 'There is no significant influence of capacity building in the management reform on service delivery at Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company.' was rejected therefore accepting the alternative hypothesis 'There is a significant influence of capacity building in the management reform on service delivery at Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company.'. This implies that capacity building had significant influence on service delivery at 5 % levels of significance.

It was concluded that capacity building in the management reforms has an important impact on delivering of services in Nakuru Water and Sanitation Services Company. Conclusions can be made that there are more service hours although there was good quality of water as an outcome of reformed administration. The outcome also indicate that respondents were of the opinion that to large extent water tariffs were affordable and held the opinion that to moderate extent water tariffs were affordable as a result of reformed management. Further, quantity of water supplied was to some extent adequate as a result of reformed management. The management reforms have a big share of the capability development of the organization with some holding a neutral opinion while a small number were in disagreement that management reforms have played a big role in the capacity building of NAWASSCO.

The researchers recommend that the organization should also recruit and deploy adequate health work force in number, qualifications and specialization to ensure quality service delivery. The staff should be adequately trained to build their capacity in the delivery of quality services.

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